

Focus Group Interview on the Evaluation of Challenges for Data Quality Issues

- 1) Introduction to focus group interviews
- 2) Presentation of challenges already identified
 - After presentation of **all** challenges, discussion about the challenges
- 3) Mapping of challenges to data quality management phases
 - Please give feedback directly

Methodology:

Focus Group Interview

- Focus group interview is a qualitative study
 - Aims at qualitative feedback: not only the individual opinions of the participants, but also the exchange and discussion process of the participants among themselves
- Objective: Insights into the attitudes and opinions of the participants
 - No adaptation to a group opinion
 - No identification with majorities/minorities
- Please take part in the discussion and give us feedback! There are no right or wrong answers.
- Results of the focus group interview are recorded and subsequently analyzed
- Question: Is it okay for you to record the focus group interview?

- **Group 1: Data type**
 - C1: Volume
 - C2: Variety
 - C3: Velocity
 - C4: Granularity
- **Group 2: Knowledge**
 - C5: New Data Quality Issues
 - C6: Rare Data Quality Issues
 - C7: Causality Ambiguity
 - C8: Solution Ambiguity
 - C9: Procedure Refinement
- **Group 3: Conflict of interest**
 - C10: Privacy
 - C11: Business Interest Conflicts
 - C12: Data Quality Issue Cascade
- **Group 4: Data quality management**
 - C13: Knowledge Representation
 - C14: Knowledge Reuse and Transfer

→ At the current point, the order of the challenges is arbitrary.

Challenges – Group 1: Data type

(1)

C1: Volume

- Refers to big data problem of the volume → Processes with many sensors (e.g. large production processes) generate a lot of data
- Detailed calculations based on this data are very computationally intensive
- Possibility of using simplified / abstracted data representation → Tradeoff compression vs information loss

C2: Variety

- Refers to big data problem of the variety → Sources are different sensors, sometimes even from different factories, which measure different values
- Multiple data types present (Boolean/binary, coordinates, etc.)
- The sensors in the factory might correlate (e.g., coordinates of a robot with the interruption of a light barrier) or not

C3: Velocity

- Refers to big data problem of the velocity → the large number of sensors (volume) within factories continuously produce data (e.g., several times per millisecond), which often need to be evaluated in real time
- DQIs can only ever be addressed in a staggered manner, the influence of a fixed error can only be examined afterward → Tradeoff between data income and DQI handling
- Is related to C1 (volume) → mutually dependent

C4: Granularity

- Question: Where are DQIs identified and treated? → E.g., at which level?
- Method / algorithm selection → after some preprocessing/ abstraction (e.g., CEP), or on the raw sensor data?
- Consideration of e.g., whether work can be carried out directly at the edge and DQIs do not need to be analyzed at factory level → but: dependencies must also be considered

C5: New Data Quality Issues

- Data quality issues that were never observed before cannot be classified automatically → (AI) model cannot know them
- Possibility of anomaly detection for initial identification, followed by retraining of the model
- Knowledge acquisition and generation problem for new DQIs → Where does the knowledge come from?

C6: Rare Data Quality Issues

- Cold Start Problem → Similar to C5 (New DQIs), but there is basic knowledge about these DQIs
- Problem of data generation as with C5 → data are very unbalanced
- Due to the rarity, the classification and retrieval of suitable solutions is difficult
- Danger of overfitting (not detecting rare DQI) when training (AI) models (as with C4)

C7: Causality Ambiguity

- DQIs can have effects on the data that cannot be mapped or recognized as a pattern. Also, patterns of different DQIs can be very similar to each other.
- For example, noisy data can be due to poorly calibrated sensor, issue in the environment (e.g., someone walking near a pressure sensor) → similar patterns but different causes

C8: Solution Ambiguity

- Complementary issue to C7: if cause is unclear, solution will likely also be ambiguous
- Sometimes, even if cause is identified correctly, there can be multiple alternative solutions

C9: Procedure Refinement

- Solutions must be checked to ensure that they really improve data quality and do not cause other problems
- If the procedure does not work as desired, it must be improved (iteratively)

Challenges – Group 3:

Conflict of Interest (1)

C10: Privacy

- Possible reason: Companies do not want to share data → Possible insight into production for competitors, competitors should not be supported
- But also “real” privacy issues may occur
- Public data sets on which procedures for DQI identification can be trained are not available
- Therefore, difficult to find data for training appropriate models or to derive general DQI patterns

C11: Business Interest Conflicts

- Interests from the DQI area (correcting errors as quickly as possible) can be contrary to business interests
- It may be that a sensor only causes small DQIs (e.g., only missing values at regular intervals), and from a predictive maintenance perspective the sensor can run for a while longer

C12: Data quality issues Cascade

- DQI messes up with process and solving DQI makes rest of process nonsense
- The following example:
 - The sensor data of a light barrier sensor is missing where a workpiece is.
 - The Gripper Robot does not pick it up because the information about the workpiece is not available.
 - This workpiece is therefore never transported any further.
 - Repairing the event log would no longer reflect the logic of the process
 - It would no longer be clear why the robot did not pick up the workpiece
 - (It is also possible that because of this there would be looked for an non existing error)

C13: Knowledge Representation

- Question: How is knowledge suitably represented?
- In particular, how the knowledge that experts have is made available to machines so that they can work with it automatically

C14: Knowledge Reuse and Transfer

- Knowledge about DQIs mostly linked to domains (factories, lines, or machines)
- However, this knowledge should be generalized as much as possible so that it can be applied or transferred to similar domains
- Question: How can suitable knowledge be identified and applied to new problems?

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Questions

- 1) Are some challenges that you are familiar with missing? Would you remove challenges?
- 2) Would you combine or split up some challenges? If yes, which ones?
- 3) Which challenges have you encountered in your use cases? Can you provide concrete examples?
- 4) How would you order the individual challenges in terms of their importance? You are welcome to do this from a specific perspective, please name it.

Background: DQI Management Cycle

Data Quality Issue Management Cycle

Mapping of Challenges to Phases

Challenge	Detection	Handling	Solving	Evaluation
C1: Volume	X	X		
C2: Variety	X	X		
C3: Velocity	X			
C4: Granularity	X	X		
C5: New Data Quality Issues	X	X	X	X
C6: Rare Data Quality Issues	X			
C7: Causality Ambiguity	X	X	X	X
C8: Solution Ambiguity	X	X	X	X

Mapping of Challenges to Phases

Challenge	Detection	Handling	Solving	Evaluation
C9: Procedure Refinement	X	X	X	X
C10: Privacy		X		X
C11: Business Interest Conflicts	X	X	X	X
C12: Data Quality Issue Cascade	X	X		
C13: Knowledge Representation	X	X	X	X
C14: Knowledge Reuse and Transfer		X	X	